

B!SON

B!SON – A Recommendation System for Open Access Journals

Sustainability, Long-Term Operation and Further Development

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Summary

B!SON, the recommendation system for Open Access journals, will continue to be made available free of charge by the Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB) after the end of the project funding (January 31, 2023). The TIB aims to operate B!SON on a permanent basis. It guarantees its availability, including updates and support, for at least five years. In order to partially compensate for the costs of operation, a model is then being sought, for instance on the basis of voluntary membership contributions by institutions or individuals. Institutions interested in using B!SON locally, for example to supplement their publication advisory services, are supported.

The source code of the recommendation system is available as free software in order to enable subsequent use, improvement and further development. Building on the underlying technologies of the recommendation system -- semantically and bibliometrically based similarity determination of scientific texts -- the partners are striving for further project projects that serve the overarching goal of supporting scholar-led Open Access publishing.

The document describes how the sustainable availability of the B!SON service is to be achieved and what approaches exist for further development of the tool.

Institutional integration of the B!SON service after the end of the project

The recommendation system for Open Access journals developed in the project "B!SON - Bibliometric and Semantic Open Access Recommender Network" will be provided by the Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB) as a free digital service after the end of the funding period.¹ With B!SON, all interested parties, especially researchers, will have the opportunity to have quality-assured OA journals suggested that match the content of a given manuscript.

B!SON thus complements the digital services that the TIB, as a scientific infrastructure and research institution of the Leibniz Association, develops and provides as part of its supra-regional tasks.² The aim is to support researchers in the various phases of the research process and at the same time to strengthen the principle of open research. The technical responsibility for B!SON lies with the Publishing Services section of the TIB's programme area Local Services. Technical support is provided by the Information Technology department and the Development section of the programme area Research and Development.

Technical operation

Software

The source code of the recommendation system is available under AGPL.³ Deployment to the server is done via Ansible. The scripts are available in an internal repository, including the secrets. The data sets obtained from OpenCitations and DOAJ (see next section) are automatically updated by means of a cron job that runs once a month.

A prototype of a TYPO3 extension under GPL is available for integrating the recommendation

1 The project was funded from April 1, 2021 to January 1, 2023 as part of the programme „Beschleunigung der Open-Access-Transformation“ (“accelerating the transformation to open access”) by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung, BMBF).

2 <https://www.tib.eu/en/services>

3 <https://gitlab.com/TIBHannover/bison>

system into third-party websites.⁴ This prototype is designed to meet the requirements of the SLUB Dresden. Besides a seamless integration into the respective web interface, the extension enables an adaptation and enrichment of the results, e.g. by means of journal and funding information specific for the respective institution.

Data sources: third-party data used for B!SON

The algorithm for matching the input data to previously published literature - with the aim of identifying suitable OA publication venues - uses (1) article metadata from the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) and (2) a citation database provided by OpenCitations. Both data sources are available under CC0 1.0 Universal (Public Domain).⁵ DOAJ also integrates a database with information on the approx. 19,000 journals listed in DOAJ (e.g. licenses, price information). This is licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0 International.⁶

DOAJ and OpenCitations are committed to the Principles for Open Scholarly Infrastructures (POSI).⁷ DOAJ is funded by voluntary contributions from numerous institutions and libraries, while OpenCitations receives funding from the academic community through the SCOSS programme.⁸ It can be safely assumed that the data corpora of DOAJ and OpenCitations - which are central to the functionality of B!SON - will be permanently updated, further developed and made available at constant conditions.

Further data sources are the Journal Checker Tool provided by cOAlition S⁹, for which it can be assumed that it will be made available permanently, as well as a free currency converter, which, due to its simple functionality, can be easily replaced in the event of a possible failure.

Hardware

The service runs on the GPU server `gpu1.research.tib.eu`, which is integrated into the IT infrastructure for digital services at TIB. In its current configuration, it uses one of the three graphics cards and <1 TB of hard disk space.

Supporting the use and popularity of the B!SON service

Individual users of B!SON are offered advice and support as needed (e-mail support, information on the website). The functionality and advantages of the system are explained, also in comparison to alternative products with similar objectives. Institutions wishing to integrate B!SON into their website will receive support in this regard. A technical solution for integration into websites is currently offered in prototype form for the content management system (CMS) TYPO3 (in addition to a simple widget). It is planned to support other CMS. Documentation materials are provided. In addition to the technical integration, institutions are supported on a professional level to integrate B!SON into their advisory services, e.g. in the form of webinars. Conditions of use are agreed with institutions that integrate B!SON (e.g. to keep the name B!SON). This can be done e.g. through a Memorandum of Understanding. The offer for B!SON integration is aimed at academic institutions, especially libraries, but also specialised information services and research funding service centers.

A high level of awareness was already achieved during the project period, especially through

4 <http://sdvtypo3bison.slub-dresden.de>

5 <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0>

6 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0>

7 <https://blog.doaj.org/2022/10/06/doaj-commits-to-the-principles-of-open-scholarly-infrastructure-posi/>, <https://opencitations.wordpress.com/2021/08/09/opencitations-compliance-with-the-principles-of-open-scholarly-infrastructure/>

8 <https://scoss.org/>

9 <https://journalcheckertool.org/>

presentations at conferences, webinars, newsletters and social networks. In order to continue to make the service known in the community in the long term, information will be included in central information resources on scientific publishing and Open Access, e.g. open-access.network¹⁰. Various formats are considered (informative websites, videos, self-learning materials, etc.). The TIB's Publication Services section offers various regional and supra-regional advisory services that can be used to publicise B!SON in institutions as well as scientific communities and societies. The service continues to be presented at relevant conferences, together with related TIB services, where appropriate. TIB's Communications department promotes B!SON, analogous to other TIB services such as the TIB AV Portal, via the channels appropriate for the respective target audience, including social networks. Feedback from the community is also taken into account in the further development of the service (see section "Conceptual and technical development").

Financing of the medium to long-term operation

The free provision of the web interface and API of B!SON and the associated support will remain guaranteed for at least five years as part of the TIB's basic tasks. While basic use and support will continue to remain free of charge in the long term, a refinancing mode is planned to partly cover the expenses for permanent operation and further development. For this purpose, a model of voluntary membership fees is being considered, for which paying institutions or users can receive certain services in return, e.g. extended functionality of the recommendation system or a more efficient API access. In the development and evaluation of suitable operating models, suggestions, feedback and requirements from the community will be included and references to comparable models that exist will be collected. Specifically for the conceptual and technical development of the B!SON, a model of one-time financial contributions for the development of certain desired functionalities or adjustments may be considered.

Conceptual and technical development

In addition to routine technical checks and updates, which are necessary to ensure that the service is running without errors, an evaluation is carried out (e.g. changed needs due to changes in the landscape of open access publishing) and, if necessary, a follow-up. The development of new digital services based on the present algorithm is being sought, analogous to the procedure for B!SON, through initial third-party funding and subsequent continued operation by the project partners. A transfer of the semantic and bibliometric procedures for determining similarity to other application scenarios in the scientific publication process or the use of other data corpora are possible lines of development.

For new projects or services based on B!SON, the principles of open, sustainable operation are equally taken into account. Resulting further developments in technology will be fed back into previously developed services such as B!SON. The involvement of data-providing partners (DOAJ, OpenCitations) will be continued and, if possible, expanded to include new partners.

As in the initial B!SON project phase, interested institutions and individuals will be actively involved in the development and regularly invited to participate in low-threshold exchange opportunities, for example to contribute feature requests. In order to further anchor the project in the community, there are cooperations with important stakeholders such as open-access.network. This is complemented by ongoing national and international networks, partnerships and projects of TIB and SLUB. The expansion of international partnerships in particular should contribute to this.

¹⁰ <https://open-access.network/en/home>